

Peer Tutoring: An Intervention to Improve Earners' Involvement in Performance Task

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Abstract

This action research focused on the effectiveness of peer tutoring in the performance task involvement of learners in Lubang National High School. The researcher aimed to improve the performance task involvement of Ninety-two (92) Grade 11 learners. The Ninety-two (92) learners or 100% very low in performance task involvement. The monitoring checklist form was used as a data-gathering tool. Frequency, percentage, and weighted mean were used as statistical treatments. The researcher addressed improving performance task involvement using Peer Tutoring. The results of the study showed that the learners' involvement in accomplishing the performance task was increased. There is a weighted mean difference of 19.47 before and after Peer Tutoring was applied. The findings stressed that there was an improvement in the learner's performance task after the implementation of peer tutoring as an intervention. It is proposed that teachers should design activities through Peer Tutoring to promote camaraderie as they continue learning and continue establishing and maintaining programs that can encourage and engage the learners to involve in accomplishing performance tasks and find more ways to maintain the very good state of willingness. Peer tutoring may help learners make connections across 21st-century skills and concepts, and other disciplines. Following the principles of Peer Tutoring, learners should have time to discuss how they perform in performance task involvement. With careful planning and implementation, performance task involvement can be achieved successfully by all learners.

Keywords: Peer Tutoring, Performance Task, Learners Involvement

Introduction

The K to 12 Basic Education Program emphasizes the integration of 21st-century skills into the teaching and learning environment. Learners are assessed in the classroom through various processes and measures appropriate and congruent to the learning competencies defined in the K to 12 curricula. Learners may be assessed individually or collaboratively. Written work, performance tasks, and quarterly assessments are the three components of classroom assessment. Performance tasks refer to assessment tasks that allow learners to show what they know and can do in diverse ways and also Performance Task has the biggest impact on the learners' grades.

Performance tasks are commonly employed in fields where performance is the natural emphasis of instruction, such as the visual and performing arts, physical education, and professional technology. Learners can engage in meaningful learning by using performance-based activities. Learners are generally motivated and engaged by such "real world" problems because rich performance-based objectives create authentic contexts that reflect genuine applications of knowledge. Learners can employ and develop their 4C skills, critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and creativity through performance tasks. Many of the

exercises are put in a global context to help learners prepare for a world that is becoming increasingly interconnected.

In DepEd Order No. 031 s. 2020 or the "Interim Guidelines for Assessment and Grading in Light of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan" No.16 states that "To evaluate student learning at particular points in each quarter, the summative assessment shall continue in the form of written works and performance tasks." It is a national order that addresses the thrust of the Department of Education (DepEd), that performance tasks should not be overlooked even in times of pandemic because it still plays a great role in the classroom assessment. However, still, learners are struggling with their involvement and accomplishing their performance tasks.

Peer tutoring is a method of learning in which learners assist one another and teach one another. Throughout the process, the learners learn from one another in an organized manner. Peer tutoring allows learners to put their prior knowledge and experience to use in a meaningful way. Peer-tutoring is one of the more extended forms to support new learners' adjustment (Kuh et al. 2006; Ruffalo Noel-Levitz 2015), and it's described as the active assisting and supporting of status equals or matched companions in the development of knowledge and skill, with both tutees and tutors benefiting from the transaction. (Topping,

2015). Peer tutoring helps develop the skills of learners to manage and plan learning experiences, work in association, give and receive responses about their activities and finally evaluate their learning.

Furthermore, Peer Tutoring is a teaching approach in which a group of students engages to aid each other's learning, with one learner serving as the tutor and the other as the tutee. Peer interaction among learners is useful in learning new skills, knowledge, and solutions to each other's problems by playing, talking, and sharing ideas. Peer tutoring helps to develop the skills of learners to manage and plan learning experiences, work in association, give and receive responses about their activities and finally evaluate their learning.

In lieu of this, the administration and staff implemented various interventions and strategies in improving learners' involvement in the performance task. However, the School Monitoring, Evaluation and Adjustment (SMEA) analysis results of Grade 11 showed that 100% or 92 out of 92 learners are very low in involvement rate on learner's performance task. The very low involvement of learners in performance tasks posed an alarming concern to the faculty and staff.

For this reason, the researcher is motivated to conduct this action research to improve learners' involvement in performance tasks among Grade 11 learners of Lubang National High School. Moreover, the peer tutoring intervention will be used to develop the skills of self-motivation in accomplishing all required academic tasks in all subject areas of Grade 11 learners and the expertise needed to effective involvement in group activities. The findings of this study will benefit the learners, teachers, parents, and school heads as it can be used as a new intervention in improving involvement on performance tasks. Furthermore, the intervention can also be replicated to schools and districts having the same problem, as another intervention that can be used at a division-wide level.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study is to determine the effectiveness of peer tutoring in improving the involvement in performance tasks of Grade 11 learners of Lubang National High School, Buenavista District in the school year 2020-2021. The following questions were specifically addressed in this study:

1. What is the level of learners' involvement in accomplishing their performance task, before and after the peer tutoring intervention?

2. Is there an improvement in the learner's performance task after the implementation of peer tutoring as an intervention?

Methodology

Participants

The researcher employed a complete enumeration. The participants were Grade 11 learners of Lubang National High School, Buenavista District. The timeframe of the research was during the first and second semesters of School Year 2020-2021. Table 1 shows the number of respondents.

Table 1. *The Participants of the Research*

<i>Grade 11 Section</i>	<i>Male</i>	<i>Female</i>	<i>Total</i>
Sincerity	19	27	46
Strength	21	25	46
Total	40	52	92

The researcher chose them as the participants because of the underlying factor that 100% or 92 out of 92 learners population are very low in terms of the level of involvement on the performance task. The reason that senior high school is new to them and that they are still adapting to the new normal of education.

This research employed a quantitative – descriptive method since the objectives of the researcher are to determine the weighted mean in the involvement of performance tasks before and after the intervention and the significant increase in the weighted mean.

The first measurement would serve as the Pre-Monitoring Checklist, the second as the Post Monitoring Checklist. The measurements would be collected.

Data Gathering Methods

The conduct of this study is presented in the conceptual schema illustrated in Figure 1. which is The Flow Chart of Accomplishing Performance Task.

As shown in the figure, the study centers on the difference between before and after peer tutoring as an intervention. The researcher aims to assess the effectiveness of Peer Tutoring in improving learners' involvement in the performance task. The level of learner involvement is obtained before and after the intervention.

Data before and after the intervention would be compared to determine the level of learners' involvement. Based on the findings, an action plan should be developed to enhance learners' involvement and improvement in accomplishing performance tasks.

Upon the approval of the letter request to the Barangay Local Government Unit (BLGU) Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF), the research proponents personally met the concerned teachers, parents, and learners and carefully explained the purpose of the study.

Figure 1. The Flow Chart of Accomplishing Performance Task

Results and Discussion

Table 2. Level of the Learners' Involvement in Accomplishing their Performance Task Before and After the Peer Tutoring Intervention (N = 92)

Involvement Range (30)	Before Intervention Frequency	Percent	After Intervention Frequency	Percent	Levels of Involvement
24 - 30	0	0	90	97.83	Very High
17 - 23	0	0	2	2.17	High
10 - 16	18	19.57	0	0	Low
3 - 9	74	80.43	0	0	Very Low
Total	92	100.00	92	100.00	
Mean	7.37 Very Low		26.84 Very High		

Table 2 shows the level of the Learners' Involvement in Accomplishing the Performance Task of Grade 11 before the Peer Tutoring Intervention based on their total number of Performance Tasks.

In the learners' involvement before the peer tutoring intervention, out of 92 Grade 11 Learners, no learners or 0% with *Very High* and *High* level of involvement. However, there are 18 or 19.57% of learners belong with a *Low* level of involvement; 74 or 80.43%, with a *Very Low* level of involvement. The mean of the learners is placed at 7.37 which means that generally, the learners have a *Very Low* level of involvement.

On the other hand, after the intervention, out of 92 Grade 11 Learners, there are 90 or 97.83% of learners who belong to the involvement range from 24-30 and that ninety learners belong to a *Very High* level of involvement. However, there are 2 or 2.17% of learners who belong to a *High* level of involvement; and, no students or 0%, with *Low* and *Very Low* levels of involvement. The mean of the learners is placed at 26.84 which means that generally, the learners have a *Very High* level of involvement in the Performance Task using Peer Tutoring as an intervention.

Table 3. Comparison of Weighted Mean in the involvement of learners on performance tasks before and after the intervention

Learners Involvement	Mean	Mean Difference	Interpretation
Before the Intervention	7.37	19.47	The mean increased by 19.47 units
After the Intervention	26.84		

Table 3 presents the simple difference between the after-intervention mean deducted from the before-intervention mean to test the increase or decrease of involvement of the 92 participating learners to arrive at the mean difference. It could be seen that the mean of the after-intervention results of the participants (29.84) is higher than the before-intervention results (7.37) by exactly a mean difference of 19.47 units.

The above findings stressed that the results after the peer tutoring intervention have a high increase. This explains that the levels of involvement of learners in the performance task have *improved*.

Conclusion

The current data show that peer tutoring is an effective intervention for improving learner involvement in performance tasks. The results of this study will benefit learners, parents, teachers, and other schools that are dealing with the same issue. The learners are the first to feel the effects of this research. It will assist the learners who have expressed an interest in working with their peers to have a high level of involvement.

This will serve as a wake-up call for parents regarding their substantial and impactful influence on their children's academic performance. This research will help teachers determine whether or not the techniques and tactics they are doing are useful, allowing them to develop new strategies and approaches to better serve their learners. Furthermore, for other schools with a similar problem, the intervention used in this study will be extremely beneficial in resolving their low involvement in performance tasks.

Finally, the learners show a high level of motivation in their unconscious processes, technique application, and collaboration with other students. They rated themselves as having extremely high levels of self-awareness and motivation.

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